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Design of stakeholder questionnaires for use in WP7

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questionnaires for use in WP7

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Introduction

Aim: A systematic screening of the key lock-ins and barriers to the sustainable use of PPPs in existing farming and food systems and the governance mechanisms for PPP will be carried out with the help of a review of literature and policy documents, and interviews with stakeholders in the CSS, as well as on national and EU level.

Interests, needs and views of farmers, farm advisors, regulators, policy makers and other societal actors related to lock-ins and barriers to more sustainable plant protection will be identified (including economic aspects). This includes farm-level lock-ins and barriers towards the wider uptake of pesticide reduction strategies (as identified in task 2.5), as well as more systemic lock-ins related to both input substitution and system redesign.

Actors: The questionnaires will gather views from all relevant types of actors in the agri-food supply chain as shown in the graphic below.

For the stakeholders in the case study areas, the questions focus on perceptions of current levels of pesticides use, and the barriers and solutions to reducing pesticide use on the farms and in the region more broadly. These questions were included in the Monitoring Plan for case studies (D2.1, in Appendix 2. Two versions of the questionnaire are available – one for farmers and one for neighbours (non-farmers) and consumers. Overall, 72 participants (36 males and 36 females) will be answering the questions in each CSS. The collected data will be used to feed into deliverable 7.1. on barriers and solutions for transition to sustainable plant protection, and will be combined with literature review (deliverable due date is October 2022).

For the stakeholders outside of the case study areas, the interviews will combine data collection for deliverables 7.1, 7.2. and 7.3. This change to the work plan has been made to avoid stakeholder fatigue and ensure that the same stakeholders contribute to identification of barriers and solutions (D7.1), the vision for end goal of the transition process (D7.2) and the transition pathways (7.3). Therefore, in the summer 2021, we will expand the questionnaires with questions relating to the visioning and pathways and establish contacts with the relevant stakeholders. An introductory online meeting with EU stakeholder will be organised on 22 June 2021. The interviews will then be conducted from Autumn 2021 through Spring 2022.

A. Appendix 2 to the monitoring plan

Questions to FARMERS in case study areas: views on pesticide application

Note to SPRINT partners: We suggest to conduct the interview face-to-face and let farmer have a copy of the questions. If the interview is conducted via phone, please email or send per post the questionnaire to farmers in advance. This will make it much easier for farmers to respond.

PARTICIPANT ID: _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _
Date of interview: _____ - _____ 2021 DROP DOWN CALENDER
Address (interview place): _____
Start time: _____
End time: _____
Interviewer ID: _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _

1. Levels of pesticide application

1a) How would you rank the levels of pesticide application on your farm?

Please choose on a scale from 1 to 7, with 1 very low and 7 very high.

1-very low

7-very high

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
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1b) How would you rank the levels of pesticide application on your neighbouring farms?

Please choose on a scale from 1 to 7, with 1 very low and 7 very high.

1-very low

7-very high

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
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Please feel free to provide any additional comments you have on pesticide application on your farm or on your neighbouring farms:

2. What are the main reasons for the current levels of pesticide application on your farm?

Please rank the following themes from 1 to 7 according to your personal preferences (1 being the most important reason, you can use the same ranking for multiple answers).

	Ranking place
Risk of yield losses	

Lack of available alternatives	
Lack of knowledge about alternatives	
Concern about impacts on the environment and/or human health	
Regulatory restrictions	
Funding to support use of alternatives	
Other – please specify	
Other – please specify	
Other – please specify	

Please feel free to provide any additional comments here:

3. In your view, what would enable a reduction in pesticide applications in farming in general?

Please name and briefly explain **the top 3 solutions** that you think would enable a reduction in pesticide applications in farming in general. The answers, for example, could relate to farm economics in general, availability and demonstration of alternatives, knowledge and advice, regulation, specific funding support etc.

	Solution and brief explanation
1	
2	
3	

1b) How would you rank the levels of pesticide application on your neighbouring farms?

Please choose on a scale from 1 to 7, with 1 very low and 7 very high.

1-very low

7-very high

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Please feel free to provide any additional comments you have on pesticide application on the farms in your area or on your neighbouring farms:

2. What do you think are the main reasons for the current levels of pesticide application on the farms in your area?

Please rank the following themes from 1 to 7 according to your personal preferences (1 being the most important reason, you can use the same ranking for multiple answers).

	Ranking place
Risk of yield losses	
Lack of available alternatives	
Lack of knowledge about alternatives	
Concern about impacts on the environment and/or human health	
Regulatory restrictions	

Funding to support use of alternatives	
Other – please specify	
Other – please specify	
Other – please specify	

Please feel free to provide any additional comments here:

3. In your view, what would enable a reduction in pesticide applications in farming in general?

Please name and briefly explain **the top 3 solutions** that you think would enable a reduction in pesticide applications in farming in general. The answers, for example, could relate to farm economics in general, availability and demonstration of alternatives, knowledge and advice, regulation, specific funding support etc.

	Solution and brief explanation
1	
2	
3	

B. Questionnaires for stakeholders who are not case study participants

These interviews will be conducted in-person or as phone interviews by Ecologic Institute. For each interview the basic information will be collected. The questions below are targeted to the specific stakeholder type; some questions are the same across the stakeholder types. The interviews will not collect sensitive data. Stakeholders will be asked if they would prefer their responses to be treated as anonymous.

<p>PARTICIPANT Name : _____</p> <p>Organisation: _____</p> <p>Date of interview: _____ - _____ 2021/2022</p> <p>Interview place: _____</p> <p>Type of stakeholder: _____</p> <p>Treat as anonymous: yes / no</p> <p>Start time: _____</p> <p>End time: _____</p> <p>Interviewer Name: _____</p>
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Governance actors / Regulators

1. Levels of pesticide application

1a) How would you rank the levels of pesticide application in farming (specific sector you are representing)

Please choose on a scale from 1 to 7, with 1 very low and 7 very high.

1-very low

7-very high

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
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Please provide additional comments you have on pesticide application levels:

2. Where do you see the main barriers to reduce pesticide use and what solutions can be pursued to address these barriers?

Please consider the following themes, specify a concrete barriers, provide explanation for why you think it is important, and rank the barriers from **1 to 7 according to your personal preferences** (1 being the most important reason, you can use the same ranking for multiple answers).

	Explanation	Ranking
Authorisation process		
Risk assessment methods		

Data and knowledge availability		
Political economy		
Funding opportunities		
Availability of alternatives		
Food security		
Other – please specify		
Other – please specify		

3. In your view, what changes in the governance and regulation would drive a reduction in pesticide applications?

Please name and briefly explain **the top 3 solutions** that you think would enable a reduction in pesticide applications. The answers, for example, could relate to farm economics in general, availability and demonstration of alternatives, knowledge and advice, regulation, specific funding support etc.

	Solution and brief explanation
1	
2	
3	

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4. Are you aware of activities or changes that are planned that would contribute to the scaling up of the solutions?

Please explain.

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5. Is there anything else you believe SPRINT project should take into account?

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Producers' organisations

1. Levels of pesticide application

1a) How would you rank the levels of pesticide application in farming (specific sector you are representing)

Please choose on a scale from 1 to 7, with 1 very low and 7 very high.

1-very low

7-very high

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Please provide additional comments you have on pesticide application levels:

2. What are the main reasons for the current levels of pesticide application in farming (specific sector you are representing)?

Please rank the following themes from 1 to 7 according to your personal preferences (1 being the most important reason, you can use the same ranking for multiple answers).

	Explanation	Ranking place
Biophysical constraints of farming without plant protection products		
Lack of available alternatives		
Lack of knowledge and advice about alternatives		

Impacts on the environment and/or human health		
Regulatory restrictions		
Monitoring and enforcement of existing legislation		
(International) competition		
Food Security		
Cheap and varied food		
Advantages for farmers		
Other – please specify		
Other – please specify		
Other – please specify		

Please feel free to provide any additional comments here:

3. In your view, what would enable a reduction in pesticide applications?

Please name and briefly explain **the top 3 solutions** that you think would enable a reduction in pesticide applications in farming in general. The answers, for example, could relate to farm economics in general, availability and demonstration of alternatives, knowledge and advice, regulation, specific funding support etc.

	Solution and brief explanation
1	

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2	
3	

4. Can you point us to examples of good practices or initiatives that are developing alternatives?

Please briefly explain.

5. Is there anything else you believe SPRINT project should take into account?

Input suppliers

1. Levels of pesticide application

1a) How would you rank the levels of pesticide application in farming (and specific sector(s) you are supplying to)?

Please choose on a scale from 1 to 7, with 1 very low and 7 very high.

1-very low

7-very high

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Please provide additional comments you have on pesticide application levels:

2. What are the main reasons for the current levels of pesticide application in farming (specific sector you are supplying to)?

Please rank the following themes from 1 to 7 according to your personal preferences (1 being the most important reason, you can use the same ranking for multiple answers).

	Explanation	Ranking place
Biophysical constraints of farming without plant protection products		
Lack of available alternatives		
Lack of knowledge and advice about alternatives		

Impacts on the environment and/or human health		
Regulatory restrictions		
Monitoring and enforcement of existing legislation		
(International) competition		
Food Security		
Cheap and varied food		
Advantages for farmers		
Other – please specify		
Other – please specify		
Other – please specify		

Please feel free to provide any additional comments here:

3. In your view, what would enable a reduction in pesticide applications?

Please name and briefly explain **the top 3 solutions** that you think would enable a reduction in pesticide applications in farming in general. The answers, for example, could relate to farm economics in general, availability and demonstration of alternatives, knowledge and advice, regulation, specific funding support etc.

	Solution and brief explanation
1	

2	
3	

4. Are you developing alternatives that would reduce the need for pesticide applications? What do you see as the barriers to scale up this (these) alternative(s) and how can these be addressed?

Please explain.

5. Is there anything else you believe SPRINT project should take into account?

Food processors and retailers

1. Levels of pesticide application

1a) How would you rank the levels of pesticide application in farming (and specific sector(s) you are sourcing from)?

Please choose on a scale from 1 to 7, with 1 very low and 7 very high.

1-very low

7-very high

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Please provide additional comments you have on pesticide application levels:

2. What are the main reasons for the current levels of pesticide application in farming (specific sector you are sourcing from)?

Please rank the following themes from 1 to 7 according to your personal preferences (1 being the most important reason, you can use the same ranking for multiple answers).

	Explanation	Ranking place
Biophysical constraints of farming without plant protection products		
Lack of available alternatives		
Lack of knowledge and advice about alternatives		

Impacts on the environment and/or human health		
Regulatory restrictions		
Monitoring and enforcement of existing legislation		
(International) competition		
Food Security		
Cheap and varied food		
Advantages for farmers		
Other – please specify		
Other – please specify		
Other – please specify		

Please feel free to provide any additional comments here:

3. In your view, what would enable a reduction in pesticide applications?

Please name and briefly explain **the top 3 solutions** that you think would enable a reduction in pesticide applications in farming in general. The answers, for example, could relate to farm economics in general, availability and demonstration of alternatives, knowledge and advice, regulation, specific funding support etc.

	Solution and brief explanation
1	

2	
3	

4. Are you developing alternatives that incentivise the need for pesticide applications? What do you see as the barriers to scale up this (these) alternative(s) and how can these be addressed?

Please explain.

5. Is there anything else you believe SPRINT project should take into account?

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6. Is there anything else you believe SPRINT project should take into account?

Consumers and general public

1. Levels of pesticide application

1a) How would you rank the levels of pesticide application in farming (specific geographic area in which you operate)?

Please choose on a scale from 1 to 7, with 1 very low and 7 very high.

1-very low

7-very high

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Please provide additional comments you have on pesticide application levels:

2. What are the main reasons for the current levels of pesticide application in farming (specific geographic area in which you operate)?

Please rank the following themes from 1 to 7 according to your personal preferences (1 being the most important reason, you can use the same ranking for multiple answers).

	Explanation	Ranking place
Biophysical constraints of farming without plant protection products		
Lack of available alternatives		
Lack of knowledge and advice about alternatives		

Impacts on the environment and/or human health		
Regulatory restrictions		
Monitoring and enforcement of existing legislation		
(International) competition		
Food Security		
Cheap and varied food		
Advantages for farmers		
Other – please specify		
Other – please specify		
Other – please specify		

Please feel free to provide any additional comments here:

3. In your view, what would enable a reduction in pesticide applications?

Please name and briefly explain **the top 3 solutions** that you think would enable a reduction in pesticide applications in farming in general. The answers, for example, could relate to farm economics in general, availability and demonstration of alternatives, knowledge and advice, regulation, specific funding support etc.

	Solution and brief explanation
1	

2	
3	

4. Are you developing initiatives that support reductions in pesticide applications? What do you see as the barriers to scale up this (these) alternative(s) and how can these be addressed?

Please explain.

5. Is there anything else you believe SPRINT project should take into account?